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**The main directions of socio-economic
development of New Uzbekistan:
problems and solutions**

MINISTRY OF HIGHER EDUCATION, SCIENCE AND INNOVATION
OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN
JIZZAKH BRANCH OF THE NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF UZBEKISTAN
NAMED AFTER MIRZO ULUGBEK

Scientific journal of Science technology & Digital finance

The main directions of socio-economic development of New Uzbekistan:
problems and solutions collection of materials of the international scientific
and practical conference on the topic

(May 6, 2024)

Jizzakh-2024

In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

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3. Kazan Federal University (Russia)
4. Fast support and result LLC
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INTRODUCTION

In our country, large-scale work is carried out on the modernization of the higher education system, the introduction of modern forms and technologies of education, the improvement of the directions of training specialists. In the strategy of action on the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, important issues of radical updating the content of Personnel Training, creating the necessary conditions for the training of highly qualified specialists on the basis of international templates are outlined. At the moment, special attention is paid to the development of the material and technical base of the Institute.

Science and innovative research in it are at the center of these changes and serve as catalysts for progress in various fields such as the exact and natural sciences, economics, Information Technology, social and humanities, and so on. The main goal in the idea of the new Uzbekistan is to open new opportunities for solving and developing technologies and current social problems by investing in research and innovation.

The problems waiting for their solution to improve the effect of reforms in this direction carried out in our republic, create conditions for the comprehensive and rapid development of the state and society, modernize our country and liberalize all spheres of life will find their solution in the process of discussions, discussions and scientific lectures between high-potential scientific schools. The conference will discuss the results of advanced fundamental and Applied Research, increasing the intellectual prestige of our country and commercializing the results of research.

The main purpose of the conference is to develop scientifically based proposals for the socio-economic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, solve the tasks facing production enterprises, educational institutions and also other industry organizations by proposing new innovative solutions, studying potential solutions. In addition, the conference aims to synchronize the results of scientific research carried out in educational institutions and research institutes. Through the Scientific Reports at our conference, we are looking forward to opening a new path for young researchers, doctoral students and very talented students to communicate with the scientific community.

As a result of the conference, the environment of mutual scientific and creative cooperation between professors, students, scientific worker-researcher, independent researcher, scientists and specialists of related fields and the exchange of feedback and experience will be created, which will be combined on the path of development of Science and technology. The conference also provides for the active promotion of the intellectual prestige of our country and the commercialization of the results of research. In short, we believe that the rapid implementation of such processes as having practical skills in the training of mature qualified specialists, gaining experience, developing the modern educational process and establishing systematic work on linking new teaching processes to industry professionals will be an impetus for us to achieve great heights.

It should be noted that special attention is paid to the reform of the educational system, the conditions being created for young people, the emergence of their abilities and talents, the formation of loyalty. After all, loyalty to the Fatherland, el-yurt, is a great virtue.

ZAMONAVIY PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALAR, DARSNING SAMARALI VA SIFATLI BO'LISHIDA "CASE-STUDY" USLUBINING O'RNI

International
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practical conference

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Annotatsiya: ushbu maqolada zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar, darsning samarali va sifatli bo'lishida "case-study" uslubining o'rnini ochib berishga qaratilgan. Bu uslub muayyan vaziyatli muammolarni yechish orqali o'rganishga asoslangan muammoli vaziyatni faol tahlil qilishdir.

Kalit so'zlar: texnologiya, "Case study" uslubi, kasbiy tayyorgarlik, layoqat, taqqoslash, tahlil.

Mamlakatimizda biz yoshlarga har bir sohada juda katta imkoniyatlar yaratib berilmoqda. Berilayotgan bu imkoniyatlardan to'g'ri va oqilona foydalana olishimiz, o'zimizni shu muqaddas zamin farzandi ekanligini anglab yeta olishimiz, shuningdek faxr va iftixor bilan mag'rurlanib yuradigan buyuk siymolarimizning davomchisi bo'lishga intilayotgan katta kuch ekanligimizni o'z tuyg'ularimizda xis qila bilishimiz va shunga mos bo'lish uchun harakat qilmog'imizni o'zimizga burch qilib olishimiz lozimdir.

Bu borada biz talaba yoshlarga o'qib, izlanishimiz, tillarni mukammal darajada o'zlashtirib olishimiz yo'lida ustozlarimiz tomonidan dars mashg'ulotlari jarayonida olib borilayotgan yangi zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar va ulardan samarali foydalanish metodikalarining o'rgatilib borilishi o'z ona tilimiz bilan birgalikda, chet tillarini ham qiziqishlar bilan tezroq va mukammal o'rganib olishga imkoniyatlardan biri bo'lmoqda desak adashmagan bo'lamiz.

Hozirgi kunda ta'lim jarayonlarini tashkil etishda texnologiyalarsiz yondoshuvni amalga oshirib bo'lmaydi. Zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar darsning samarali va sifatli bo'lishiga, ta'lim-tarbiya olayotgan o'quvchi yoshlarning mustaqil va kreativ fikr yuritish ko'nikmalarini oshirib borishga turtki bera oladi. Ayniqsa bugungi kun yoshlari intilib, harakat qilayotgan chet tillarini o'rganishda, bu zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalarning ahamiyati juda kattadir.

Shunday texnologiyalardan biri, "Case study" uslubining chet tillarini o'qitishdagi ahamiyatining qisqacha tahliliga qarab chiqamiz.

"Case-study" uslubi - bu muayyan vaziyatli muammolarni yechish orqali o'rganishga asoslangan muammoli vaziyatni faol tahlil qilish usuli.

Keys-tadqiqot uslubining mohiyati: o'quvchilar vaziyatni tahlil qilishlari, muammo mohiyatini tushunishlari, mumkin bo'lgan yechimlarni taklif etishlari va ularning eng maqbulini tanlashlari kerak.

"Case-study" uslubining maqsadi- talabalar guruhining umumlashgan kuchi bilan ishning aniq holatidan kelib chiqadigan vaziyatni, ya'ni aniq ish jarayonida namoyon bo'ladigan "Case"ni tahlil qilish, amaliy yechimlarini ishlab chiqish va ularni taqdimot etishdan iborat. Jarayonning tugashi- taklif etilgan variantlarni baholash va ularning ichidan eng samaralisini tanlashdir.

"Case-study" uslubini ta'lim tizimi amaliyotiga joriy etish muammosi bugungi kunning juda dolzarb vazifalariga aylanishi ikkita g'oya asosida yuzaga kelgan:

- birinchisi, ta'lim rivojlanishining umumiy yo'nalganligidan kelib chiqadi, uning mo'ljali aniq bilimlar berishgina emas, balki shaxsning kasbiy tayyorgarligiga layoqatliligini, aqliy faoliyat ko'nikmasini, malakasini, qobiliyatini rivojlantirish bo'lib, ularning orasida o'qitish qobiliyatiga, fikrlash paradigmasining o'zgarishiga, katta hajmdagi axborotlarni qayta ishlash ko'nikmasiga alohida e'tibor qaratiladi;

- ikkinchisi, birinchi g'oya talablarini qanoatlantirishdan tashqari, turli vaziyatlarda muqobil xulq qobiliyatiga ega bo'lishi, inqirozli sharoitlarda harakatining tizimliliigi va samaradorligi bilan ajralib turishi zarur bo'lgan, mutaxassis sifatiga qo'yiladigan talablarning o'sishidan kelib chiqadi [1].

Bundan ko'rishimiz mumkinki, xorijiy tillar, jumladan ingliz tilini o'qitish jarayonida o'quvchilarning qabul qilish qobiliyatlaridan kelib chiqib matnlarni sodda va murakkablik darajalariga e'tibor qaratish, katta hajmdagi axborotlarni qayta ishlash ko'nikmasini shakllantirishda kommunikativ kompetensiyalariga alohida e'tibor berish kerak bo'ladi. Bunda o'quvchilardan til o'rganishda sizga qiyinchilik keltirib chiqarayotgan vaziyatlar, ularni yengillashtirishda, jumladan so'zlarni yod olib qolish bilan bog'liq holatlarni yaxshilashda ko'proq kitoblar ma'qul keladimi, yoki texnik vositalar yordamida amalga oshiriladigan ishlar ma'qul keladimi, degan savollar berib borilishi ularni bu borada fikr aytishga undaydi.

Aytayotgan fikrlarni hal etishda mos yo'nalishlarga doir savollar quydagicha bo'lishi mumkin:

- 1) vaziyat (masala)ni tahlil qilish ("Nima uchun... muhim?", ... nima uchunligini tushuntiring")
- 2) tahlil (xulosa) ("...dalil va hodisalar")ning kuchsiz va kuchli tomonlari nimada?");
- 3) taqqoslash-qarama-qarshi qo'yish ("bular o'rtasida qanday farq mavjud?", "O'xshash natijalarni taqqoslang");
- 4) turli yechimlar izlash ("Yana qanday yo'llar orqali yechim topish mumkin?") kabi savollar bilan murojat qilish, kerakli javoblarni tinglab, ijobiy va salbiy jihatlarini tushinib yeta olishga o'rgatib bormog'miz lozimdir.

Xulosa o'rnida shu narsaga amin bo'ldimki, bugungi rivojlanayotgan jamiyatda har bir yosh avlod o'z kelajagini yorqin tasavvur qila olishida zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalardan ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonlarida unumli foydalanib, xorijiy tillarni o'rganish, o'z fikr-mulohazalarini boshqa tillarda ham yetkazib bera olish ko'nikma va malakalarini shakllantirish borish, eng asosiysi kompetensiyaviy rivojlanishga erishishi mumkin.

Foydalangan adabiyotlar:

1. PF - 23678 sonli, Mamlakatimiz ta'lim-tarbiya tizimini yanada takomillashtirish, ilm-fan sohasi rivojini jadallashtirishga oid qo'shinch chora-tadbirlar to'g'risida.
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